

THE IMPACT OF ONLINE TEACHING ON HIGHER EDUCATION TEACHER'S PROFICIENT PERSONALITY AND THE ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract

The central ideal of this exploration is to explore how online literacy is changing both preceptors and the teaching profession in advanced education. As part of this investigation, I delved the impact of online teaching on the professional personality of preceptors who have transitioned to the online classroom. I also considered the part played by technology in this process. Previous exploration has shown that developing a stable teaching personality is a crucial element in schoolteacher retention (Danielewicz, 2001), as well as a critical contributor to success and effectiveness in the classroom (Alsup, 2005; Day et al., 2006). I contend that a stable teaching personality is inversely important for online preceptors.

Alsup argues that, when brazened with circumstances at odds with important aspects of their beliefs about teaching and literacy, preceptors initiate a process of professional uniqueness renegotiation in order to resolve the conflict caused by the discordant circumstances at hand (Alsup, 2005). This is likely to be particularly true for online preceptors. A teaching and literacy experience deprived of face-to-face relations is a major source of conflict. In order to successfully acclimate to the unique conditions of the online classroom, preceptors need to rethink beliefs and values about what it means to be a schoolteacher, both virtually and theoretically.

Keywords : *online learning, teaching profession, advanced education, abecedarian values and beliefs, technology.*

I. Introduction

Over the past decade, the setting out of online education has full-grown exponentially. Online literacy in education has gone from experimental innovation to an

almost ubiquitous teaching tool. Moment, over three- diggings of council chairpersons (77) report that their institution now offers online courses (Taylor, Parker, Lenhart & Moore, 2011), online literacy registrations are growing ten times faster than traditional registrations, and thirty-one percent of all advanced education scholars now take at least one course (Allen & Seaman, 2010). Given the growth of online literacy, it's likely that both current and unborn faculty will be engaged in some form of online literacy at some point in their career. In 2009, one-third of the professors charted by Sloan-C taught at least one online course, and one in four taught online at check-in time (Seaman, 2009).

While the overall impact of online literacy on the academy remains to be assessed, the impact is declining to be variable. Given the current economics of advanced education, it's likely that advanced education institutions (and scholars) will continue to take advantage of the numerous benefits of studying online. From an institutional viewpoint, online literacy is an affordable way to increase pupil registration and earnings without having to make corresponding investments in structure. In addition, by removing the need for physical presence in the classroom, online literacy has the implicit to make education accessible to a much larger population, while accommodating the demands of a presto- paced and global society.

Scholars profit from the inflexibility of online and cold-blooded degree programs that allow them to integrate their professional and particular lives, while remaining competitive in fleetly evolving professional geographies. This disquisition of the impact of online teaching on advanced education faculty's teaching profession builds upon previous work in three main areas 1) the state of online literacy in advanced education and schoolteacher medication to educate online; 2) exploration on profession and its externalization both in the physical and the virtual classroom; and 3) the technologies of distance literacy and their affordances for profession agreement. This section reviews the most applicable previous work in each of these three areas.

Online Teaching Learning

1. Distance Education

“Distance learning involves interesting practices of study that do not stop, with the instantaneous observation of the teachers present in the lecture room or with their scholars, but still benefit from their planning, guidance and teaching. A tutorial association” (quoted in Holmberg, 1986, p26, Larreamendy-Joerns & Leinhardt, 2006, p568).

There are numerous contending delineations for distance literacy, e-learning, web-grounded literacy, network-grounded literacy and online literacy. The Sloan-Consortium 1 (Sloan-C) developed the delineations presented below for the purpose of the large-scale quantitative data collection they conduct every time.

2. Face-to-Face Learning :

"There is no curriculum using online technology" (Allen and Simon, 2003, p6). Zero percent of the curriculum is offered online in a traditional learning environment.

3. Web Facilitated :

"Courses that use web-based technology to simplify face-to-face courses. Use the Course Management System (CMS) or web pages to post courses and assignments" (Allen and Simon, 2003, p6). One to twenty-nine percent of the courses are offered online in a web-enabled environment.

4. Blended/Hybrid Learning :

A course that combines online and face-to-face delivery. Significant amounts of content are distributed online, usually using online discussions, and the number of face-to-face meetings is generally low" (Allen and Simon, 2003, p6). Thirty to seventy-nine percent of the courses are delivered online in a mixed learning environment.

5. Online Learning :

"A course where most or all of the content is distributed online. Usually there are no face-to-face meetings" (Ellen and Simon, 2003, p6). At least eighty percent of the courses are offered online.

III. Learning Outcomes

Comparing online and face-to-face courses is a complex and potentially deceptive bid. Online literacy issues are told by a variety of factors including scholars' provocation and demographics, educational design and strategies, as well as technology choices. These factors can uniquely affect online curricula, thus threatening the validity and reliability of relative approaches. Still, the straightforward approach of relative studies is compelling. Since online courses originally replicated face-to-face courses, the temptation to compare the two surroundings is hard to repel. In the last decade, two major studies have tried to probe the value of online literacy by conducting meta-analyses. Within the field of distance education itself, previous exploration has concentrated on scholars and educational approaches. Issues related to preceptors' gestures are generally under-delved, although the shift in places and liabilities endured by online preceptors

doesn't drop their significance in the online classroom, just as “the virtual presence of an educator doesn't dwindle the central part of teaching” (Garrison & Anderson, 2000, p89). In addition, being exploration on preceptors’ geste has substantially concentrated on the identification of practical walls.

IV. Practical Barriers To Online Teaching

1. Pedagogy and Technology
2. Student Readiness
3. Time Commitment and Compensation
4. Comprehensions of Online Learning

V. Online Teaching Personalities/ Characters

Having made the decision to educate online, preceptors are faced, frequently alone and unrehearsed, with the challenge of performing in an entirely technology-intermediated terrain, where rules and actions are radically different. “There is no past history or tradition for this extraordinary semi-real, semi-fiction learning.” There are no routines governing virtual commerce that scholars have absorbed as they’ve made their way through times of training. There are no morals for their geste in these classrooms” (Polin, 2004, p43).

Paulin further claims that "in this new field, we are art workers, casting interactive spaces, tools and meaningful objects; places and personalities for actors; and ethics to carry." (Polin, 2004, p44). There's veritably little exploration on the way preceptors manage their profession in online courses. Exploration on print operation and quality in online communities suggests that moment’s druggies of technology substantially attempt to bear what they perceive as they real characters “Although online surrounds give unique openings to manage prints, for the utmost part these prints were grounded on socially desirable aspects of offline personality and a desire to present an authentic print” (Chester & Bretherton, 2007, p233).

It's important to note that this exploration of Chester & Bretherton wasn't conducted with preceptors in an educational environment, but rather with undergraduate scholars in a social environment. In discrepancy, a thing of my exploration is to explore whether preceptors’online individualities follow this pattern, or whether preceptors, pressed to borrow new pedagogical practices more acclimated to the mediated nature of the online classroom, end up creating indispensable professional rates.

VI. Technology Packages

Moment, utmost distance education programs use Course Management Systems (CMS) to deliver their courses. Still, the growing fashionability, inflexibility and versatility of social media platforms make them presumptive druthers to CMS.

1. The Course Management System
2. Social Media
3. From Text to Virtual Reality
 - a. Text- Grounded Technologies
 - b. Audio and Video Based Technology
4. Virtual Reality Exploring Personality Structure

VII. Conclusion

Online literacy is changing both preceptors and the teaching complete personality within advanced education, why numerous schoolteacher remain indecisive about online teaching, and put forward ways to report these challenges.

The changes brought upon preceptors by online teaching are transformative rather than incremental. Those preceptors who are resistant to these changes tend to acclimate inadequately to the online classroom, and frequently condemn their lack of satisfaction on the failings of the modality. This exploration also stressed the decreasingly important part that technological proficiency plays in the teaching profession. Historically, being technology inclined was noway a demand to enter the academe and succeed as a advanced education faculty member. Still, just as technology has come an essential part of the way we fraternize, work and communicate, it's getting an essential part of the way we educate and learn, and by extension, an important part of faculty's professional quality.

This study highlighted the importance of institutional and peer support in the successful transition process online. The quality of a community and the individual individualities of its members are mutually native. Therefore, for faculty to be willing to integrate online teaching with their professional individualities, advanced education institutions need to offer support for this modality by making online education a part of their institutional quality.

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